

Green Synthesis and Characterization of *Moringa Oleifera* Leaf Extract-Loaded Silver Nanoparticles and Evaluation of Antibacterial Activity

Arindam Chakraborty¹, Debdip Mandal², Rounak Seal², Soukat Garain³, Mahafuz Sahana¹, Umme Habiba², Indranil Karmakar³, Sourav Jana¹ & Payel Mukherjee²

¹School of Pharmacy, Seacom Skills University, Kendradangal, Bolpur, Birbhum, West Bengal, India, 731236

²Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, M.R. College of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Bira, Balisha, North 24 Pgs, West Bengal 743702

³Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Birbhum Pharmacy School, Bandhersole, Birbhum, West Bengal 731124

ABSTRACT

Nanoparticles are the emerging topic of research in the biomedical field. Nanoparticles are defined as the particles that have size between the range of 1 and 100 nanometers (nm) in diameter. Silver nanoparticles are most widely used because of the small size of particles, Control release of the drug Due to the small size of particles, improves bioavailability, Increase therapeutic activity. Method: In this study, Silver nanoparticles with *Moringa oleifera* leaves extract were synthesized and for the confirmation of nanoparticle formulation different characterization tests were performed such as UV-visible spectroscopy, FTIR- spectroscopy, DLS, Zeta potential and TEM analysis. To know the presence of phytochemical constituents several phytochemical tests also performed. Antimicrobial test against gram (+) (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and gram (-) (*Escherichia coli*) bacteria also performed in this study. Result: The colour shift verified that AgNP was formulated. At 218 nm, the UV-visible spectrograph displayed an absorption peak. The FTIR study's data unequivocally demonstrated that the strong absorption peaks were located between 350 and 4000 cm⁻¹. *Moringa oleifera*-loaded silver nanoparticles have a size of 57.28 nm according to dynamic light scattering (DLS), while their Z-average value (D.NM) is 133.5 nm. In contrast, the average particle size distribution in TEM examination falls between 20 and 50 nm. The produced silver nanoparticle is antibacterial against both gram (-) *Escherichia coli* and gram (+) *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Keywords: Silver nanoparticles, Green synthesis, *Moringa oleifera*, Characterization of silver nanoparticles, Antimicrobial study.

INTRODUCTION

A nanoparticles are defined as the particles that have miniature size between the range of 1 and 100 nanometers (nm) in diameter, this tiny size particles have different kinds of physical or chemical properties such as colloidal properties and electrical properties. There are several methods of synthesis of nanoparticles including synthetic, organic and physical. The synthetic method requires short periods of times but it is not eco-friendly and might be toxic for the presence of chemical agents. Organic or

biological green synthesis method is one of the most effective, safe and eco-friendly methods. The plant is used in green synthesis is nontoxic and non-hazardous in nature and sometimes the plant is used in green synthesis may contain lots of medicinal properties that could be more beneficial and enhance the effectiveness of nanoparticles. The green synthesis of nanoparticles from plant extract is great approaches that most widely used in recent studies or research. There are several experiments are performed on the synthesis of nanoparticles using medicinal plants [1–3]. Due to Small size of particles, Control release of

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drug, better therapeutic activity & bioavailability nanoparticles have gained a spotlight in research field. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are metal based nanoparticles, the particle size range between 1nm to 100 nm. Silver nanoparticles used in different field such as food, medical, healthcare and industries, due to their physio-chemical properties [4]. Silver nanoparticles have lots of biological application such as Anti-bacterial, Anti-viral, Anti-fungal, Anti-inflammatory, Drug carrier, Textiles, Bio-sensing, Anti-tumor etc. Size, size distribution, shape, morphology, composition, agglomeration, dissolving rate, particle reactivity in solution, ion release efficiency, and other parameters all affect AgNPs' biological activity.[5-7]. Synthetic or chemical methods of nanoparticles synthesis and stabilization are noxious and contrary to conversation; meanwhile biological methods of nanoparticle synthesis are safe and non-toxic product. Using Plants extract is a better plan of action for nanoparticle synthesis just because they are free from noxious chemicals as well as provide natural capping agent [8-9].The plant extracts also reduce the cost of microorganism's separation and culture media preparation that enhancing the cost of nanoparticles synthesis [10]. Antibiotic resistance the ability of a microorganism to resist the effects of an antibiotic, which become a serious problem in human health; for that reason, strong initiative should be taken for this. Silver nanoparticles have gained so much attention for having excellent antimicrobial efficacy against multi-drug resistance bacteria, viruses and other various eukaryotic microorganisms. It is therefore demonstrated that the use of green produced Ag-NPs has antibacterial efficacy against certain drug-resistant bacteria. However, much research is needed to determine whether they could be a viable treatment and preventative option for infections that are resistant to many drugs.[11,12]. In this research we planned rapid green synthesis of silver nanoparticles with the simplest, cost -effective, non-toxic, eco-friendly method using *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract which has a significant potency against different types of gram positive and gram negative microorganisms.

2. Methods:

2.1. Culture media and chemicals: Nutrient media and chemicals were collected from Hi Media

Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai,India & Merck Ltd., Mumbai,India and Amoxicillin drug (considered as standard) were collected from Cipla Ltd., India.

2.2. Bacterial strains: Two types of bacterial strains were used in this study such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram positive) & *Escherichia coli* (gram negative) both the strains were isolated in our Pharmaceutical Biotechnology laboratory [13].

2.3. Collection of *Moringa oleifera* leaves: Fresh *Moringa oleifera* leaves was collected form the village of Khandagram, Dubrajpur, Birbhum, Pin-731124, in the month of April, 2023

2.4. Preparation of leaf extract from *Moringa oleifera* leaves: The *Moringa oleifera* leaves washed and cleaned with the potable water and then double distilled water to take out the dirt and the dust particles in the leaves . After that the leaves was slightly dried in sunlight and chopped into smaller pieces. 20 g of subtly chopped *Moringa oleifera* leaves were added up to 100 ml double –distilled water and boiled for 10 minutes [14]. After boiling, the extract was separated and filtered out by using Whatman filter paper no 1 and funnel. Then, the plant extract was transferred in 500 ml beaker, cover it by aluminium foil and stored until further use[15,16].

Figure 1: Preparation of leaf extract from *Moringa oleifera* leaves

2.5. Phytochemical screening and Qualitative analysis [9,17]: Various phytochemical analyses were conducted to find out to detect the presence or absence of different types of phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, Glycosides, Saponin, Flavonoids,

Tannins or phenolic compound and carbohydrates in the leaf extract of *Moringa oleifera*[18,19].

2.6. Organoleptic Properties of *Moringa oleifera* leaf: The organoleptic properties is an important consideration in the green synthesis. In this research organoleptic studies of *Moringa oleifera* like appearance, colour, odour, taste, size, shape, state etc. were performed [20,21].

2.7. Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles: 100 ml of 10⁻³ M silver nitrate (AgNO₃) were prepared in a beaker. Next, 5 ml of silver nitrate solution were added to a

test tube containing 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 ml of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract. The test tubes were then incubated for 24 hours at 30-35 °C in a dark environment to prevent the photoactivation of silver nitrate. The color shifts from colourless to brown. The development of nanoparticles is shown by this color shift. [5,22,23]

2.8. Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles:

2.8.1. Colour Change: Colour change indicates the formation of nanoparticles [24].

Figure 2: Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles by using *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract [15]

2.8.2. UV–vis spectroscopy: The optical characteristics of biosynthesized silver nanoparticles are mostly observed using UV-vis spectroscopy. Samples were examined at room temperature using a Shimadzu 1780 UV-vis spectrophotometer set to work at wavelengths between 200 and 600 nm.[25].

2.8.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy: Following the full reduction of silver nitrate ions by *Moringa oleifera* extract, an FT-IR Spectrometer is used to examine potential functional groups contained in the silver nanoparticles [7,9]. The KBr pellet procedure was utilized to prepare the sample after the solutions were dried at 75° C and the dried powders were characterized in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ range.[26].

2.8.4. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and Zeta Potential: Detection of particle size is one of the major parameter for characterization of silver nanoparticle. For the detection of particle size we performed DLS analysis by using Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments) A few drops of concentrated silver nanoparticle (100µg/mL) were added to 10mL of Millipore water after it had been sonicated for two to three minutes. Following the successful dispersion of the nanoparticle in water, the samples were examined, and the Zeta analyzer was used to determine the particle charges.[27,28].

2.8.5. High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy: The morphological characteristics and the size of synthesized *Moringa olifera* leaf extract silver nanoparticles were visualized using HR-TEM

(Jeol 2100 plus). Particle size was calculated using Image J software.

2.8.6. Antimicrobial Study: For the observation of antimicrobial study, cup-plate or disc-diffusion method was performed. The overnight culture of *staphylococcus aureus*, which is gram positive microorganism and *E. coli*, which is gram negative microorganism were spread into the prepared nutrient agar plates. Then three cups are prepared by using aseptic cork borer in the plates and each of the cup filled with a standard sample solution, which was

Amoxicillin (10 µg/mL)[13,14]. Leaf extract of *Moringa oleifera* (10µg/mL) and silver nanoparticles of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract (10 µg/mL). Then plates are incubated in incubator at 37°C temperature for 48 hour. After that zone of inhibition were counted[13,29,30].

3. RESULTS

3.1. Screening for phytochemicals and qualitative analysis:

Table- 1: Screening for phytochemicals and qualitative analysis

Constituents	Test	Inference/ results	
		Positive	Negative
Alkaloids	Wagner's test	Yes	No
	Mayer's test	Yes	No
	Hager's test	Yes	No
	Dragendroff's test	Yes	No
	Tannic acid test	Yes	No
Glycosides	Borntrager's test	Yes	No
	Keller-Killiani test	Yes	No
	Baljet test	Yes	No
	Modified Borntrager's test	Yes	No
Saponin	Foam test	Yes	No
Flavonoids	Sulphuric acid test	Yes	No
	Shinoda test	Yes	No
Tannins or phenolic compounds	Iodine test	Yes	No
Carbohydrates	Molisch's test	Yes	No
	Fehling's test	Yes	No
	Benedict's test	Yes	No

Figure 3: Screening for phytochemicals and qualitative analysis

3.2. Organoleptic Properties of *Moringa oleifera* leaf

SL.No.	Organoleptic Properties	Observation
1	Colour	Green
2	Odour	Slightly grassy aroma
3	Taste	Slightly bitter
4	Size	Leaflets averaging 1-2 cm in length and 0.5-1 cm in width.
5	Shape	Oval to Ovate
6	State	Solid

3.3. Characterization of nanoparticles:

3.3.1. Colour Change: The colour shifts from colourless to brown. The development of nanoparticles is shown by this colour shift.

3.3.2. UV-vis spectroscopy: The absorbance of synthesized *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts loaded

Silver nanoparticles was performed by UV-vis spectrometer (8,12).The spectrum of the *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract loaded nanoparticle has maximum absorbance peak at 218 nm. Surface Plasmon resonance peak at range of 200-600 nm. From this we can conclude that the proper synthesis of silver nanoparticle (11-17).

Figure 4: UV-vis spectroscopy

3.3.3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy: The *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract and the resultant nanoparticles were characterized by FT-IR analysis. It is used to measure artificially produced silver

nanoparticles in order to determine whether there may be a protein-silver nanoparticle interaction. The FTIR study's results unequivocally demonstrated that the strong absorption peaks were located between 350 and 4000 cm^{-1} (25-30).

Serial No.	Wave No.	Bond
1	3434.7	Hydroxy group H bonded, OH stretch
2	2963.4	Methyl group
3	1384.4	Dimethyl or isomethyl group
4	1261.3	Aromatic ether, Aryl-O-Stretch
5	1093.5	Cyclic ether, C-O stretch
6	1020.8	Aliphatic fluoro compound, C-F stretch
7	799.3	Aliphatic chloro compound, C-L stretch

Figure 5: Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

3.3.4. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and Zeta Potential: The size of the silver nanoparticles loaded with *Moringa oleifera* is 57.28 nm, according to the dynamic light scattering (DLS) size distribution

histogram. Z-average value(D.NM) is 133.5nm, the Polydispersity index is 0.494. Overall, the size of the silver nanoparticle is ‘Good’(17-19). Charge of silver nanoparticles was -19.2mV.

Z-Average (d.nm): 133.5	Peak 1: 57.28	% Number: 99.9	St Dev (d.nm): 21.23
Pdi: 0.494	Peak 2: 841.2	% Number: 0.0	St Dev (d.nm): 342.0
Intercept: 0.836	Peak 3: 0.000	% Number: 0.0	St Dev (d.nm): 0.000
Result quality: Good			

Figure 6: Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Figure 7: Zeta Potential

3.3.5. HR-TEM analysis: Silver nanoparticles were found to have a spherical shape and size distribution between 20 and 50 nm by HR-TEM investigation.

HR-TEM result satisfied the DLS result and proved in the range of Nanoparticles.

Figure 8: HR-TEM

3.3.4. Antimicrobial Study:

3.3.4.1. Antimicrobial activity of Ag Nanoparticle against *Staphylococcus aureus*

Serial No.	Name Of Sample	Antimicrobial Activity	Zone Of Inhibition
1	Standard (Amoxicillin)	yes	1.7cm
2	Extract of <i>Moringa oleifera</i>	yes	1.7cm
3	Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs)	yes	1.5cm

Figure 9: Antimicrobial study of silver nanoparticles against gram

positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*).

3.3.4.2. Antimicrobial activity of Ag Nanoparticle against *E. coli*:

Serial No.	Name Of Sample	Antimicrobial Activity	Zone Of Inhibition
1	Standard (Amoxicillin)	yes	2.2cm
2	Extract of <i>Moringa oleifera</i>	yes	1.8cm
3	Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs)	yes	1.8cm

Figure 10: Antimicrobial study of silver nanoparticles against gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*).

DISCUSSION

Green synthesis of nanoparticles is eco-friendly, effective, safe, no harmful & easy method. When metal nanoparticles are synthesized by green synthesis method, it became more potent & effective, zero toxicity and good therapeutic activity. Due to its rapid synthesis and lots of positive health activity, today's modern world following this procedure to get better advancement formulation and successful results. Silver is a metal and itself an antibacterial and antifungal agent that some time show bactericidal and bacteriostatic activity on the wide range of bacteria. Silver is also showing potent therapeutic activity. Due to silver is safe in nature, have no toxic activity and budget friendly compare than other metal, it would be best in targeted drug delivery. We know that nanoparticles are controlled dosages form that released the drug in targeted site and within very low dose it gives good therapeutic activity. Consequently, employing plant extract to create silver nanoparticles in an environmentally friendly manner; it truly advances formulation method that will work in proper targeted area of diseases. In this study, we used plant extract of *Moringa Oleifera* leaves for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles. The moringa also have lot of pharmacological activity like antihypertensive, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, hepatoprotective, anti-ulcer activity etc. The extract acts as a natural reducing and capping agent. DLS, HR-TEM analysis, FT-IR Spectroscopy and UV-Visible spectroscopy are some of the techniques used to characterize the synthesized nanoparticles. The UV-Visible spectrograph detected an absorbance peak at 218 nm. The FTIR investigation revealed that significant absorption peaks were seen at around 350 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} . DLS research reveals that *Moringa*

oleifera-loaded silver nanoparticles had a size of 57.28 nm and a Z-average value (D.NM) of 133.5 nm. In TEM examination, the average particle size distribution is in the region of 20 to 50 nanometers. Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) and gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) bacteria were both susceptible to the antibacterial effects of silver nanoparticles.

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